

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BEDADA****FIRST NAME: ALEMU****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: Microsoft 365 on Windows 11

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Plagiarism Avoidance: A Personal Reflection (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33-39)
2. Microsoft Word Proficiency: A Practical Skill (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 11)
3. Critical Thinking and Argumentation: Developing an Essential Mindset (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 9-10)
4. Writing as a Process: Embracing Iteration (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 10-13)

RESPONSE PAPER ON ACA-401 COURSEPACK

1)INTRODUCTION

The ACA-401 Coursepack is a valuable tool for improving my writing skills at my educational level. This coursepack emphasizes the importance of developing academic writing skills. It further teaches students to avoid plagiarism when drafting academic papers. It also informs students to cite information from other sources correctly and appropriately. This course's guidelines suit scholarly conduct at this level. Beyond its foundational principles, this course material is a practical handbook for writing essential academic and professional papers. This fifth edition adequately addresses various important topics, including proper essay composition, proper use of nuances of punctuation, plagiarism, and adherence to specific styles of conventions. For me, joining Euclid University as a new student, this coursepack is a vital resource. It gives me essential skills for effective academic and professional communication.

2) PLAGIARISM AVOIDANCE: A PERSONAL REFLECTION

The section from the course material explains how important it is to avoid plagiarism. It also defines academic dishonesty and explains the difference between intentional and unintentional plagiarism. That crucial information is essential to writing educational and professional papers (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33-39). The course teaches students strategies to master citation and good paraphrasing practices. This section motivated me to examine and evaluate my academic habits deeply and cultivate awareness to a high degree. It also provides good information on the serious consequences of academic misconduct during my university academic journey and my future professional life. That explains that ethical responsibility is not simply a set of rules to follow but is crucial to building trust and credibility in any field.

3) MICROSOFT WORD PROFICIENCY: A PRACTICAL SKILL

The coursepack identified the importance of understanding Microsoft Word proficiency. That is important for me on a practical level. It is essential to utilize it for my response paper templates. It also helps me to understand the use of advanced software features. That shows the course's commitment to helping me grasp tangible skills as a new student (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 11). Based on my experience, even if I possess basic word processing skills, I can understand that mastering features like the "Styles" and "Review" tabs will positively increase my efficiency and professional polish for my written work. I am happy that this course will narrow the gap between my understanding of practical writing and effectively applying it using relevant technology.

4) CRITICAL READING AND ARGUMENTATION: DEVELOPING AN ESSENTIAL MINDSET

The coursepack's introduction to critical reading and argumentation is the most valuable information in fostering an analytical mindset. Essential tools and strategies evaluate source credibility. In addition, it helps me to recognize potential biases and identify logical fallacies to navigate the complexities of academic discourse (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 9-10). Moreover, the part that emphasizes argument structure with evidence-based reasoning and the strategic use of counterarguments provides an essential framework for constructive and well-supported arguments (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 9-10). That perfectly aligns with my goal to become a critical thinker who can contribute meaningfully to scholarly and professional conversations. In addition, the insights into the instructor's paper review process, including an exemplary student response, provide invaluable guidance to improve my writing and understanding of expected academic assignments (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 10).

5) WRITING AS A PROCESS: EMBRACING ITERATION

The course pack emphasizes writing as a process, with detailed guidance on outlining, drafting, and revising, clarifying the part that is usually intimidating work of academic writing. In addition, this course pack helps me understand that fundamental academic communication is not a one-time event but a result of continuous refinement (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 10-12). This aligns with my understanding of effective writing, which requires time, patience, and a willingness to revise and improve. I also like the course pack's perspective, which effectively prepares me as a student for other study periods by preventing future topics and methodologies (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 12-13). From my understanding, this approach will help me build a solid foundation for continued academic and professional development.

6) CONCLUSION

The ACA-401 Coursepack is an excellent tool for academic success. Reading the material thoroughly provides a good understanding of integrity, and critical thinking helped me to understand and utilize all the tools required to accomplish university-level studies. As my introduction to academic conventions, this coursepack provides simple instruction. Moreover, it will serve as a transformative lesson that guides me as a new student toward adopting the mindset that helps me practice as a responsible and thoughtful person. The coursepack's depth covered essential points like essay composition, punctuation rules, and plagiarism avoidance.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.